

SUBSTITUTED BUTYRO LACTONES. PART I. SYNTHESIS OF γ -(4-ALKOXY-3-XENYL)-BUTYRO LACTONES

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β -(4-Alkoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionic acids have been prepared and reduced by hydrogen in presence of Raney nickel. The resulting hydroxy-acids have been lactonised.

The lactone ring is one of the important structural features of santonin and is responsible for the development of anthelmintic properties (Baldwin, *Brit. J. Pharmacol.*, 1943, 3, 91). Several substituted phenylbutyro lactones possessing anthelmintic activity have been synthesised (Rosenmund and Schapiro, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1934, 272, 313; Nargund *et al.*, *J. Indian Med. Assoc.*, 1945, 14, 69, 73).

Carbamates of 2-hydroxydiphenyl show anthelmintic properties (Burger, "Medical Chemistry", 1951, p. 925). It was of considerable interest to study compounds having a lactone ring attached to a diphenyl group containing an alkoxy group as a substituent. γ -*p*-alkoxybutyro lactones have been shown to exhibit anthelmintic properties (Trivedi and Nargund, *J. Univ. Bombay*, 1942, 11, Part III, 127; Nargund *et al.*, *loc. cit.*).

β -(4-Alkoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionic acids required for this purpose were prepared by the method of Fieser and Bradsher (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, 58, 1738). These keto-acids were reduced by hydrogen in presence of Raney nickel and the resulting hydroxy-acids were lactonised by heating them with sulphuric acid.

EXPERIMENTAL

4-Alkoxydiphenyls were prepared from 4-hydroxydiphenyl and appropriate alkyl halide in presence of sodium ethoxide in 75-80% yield (Gray *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 1419). Condensation of 4-alkoxydiphenyls with succinic anhydride and the separation of isomers were carried out as described by Fieser and Bradsher (*loc. cit.*). Only β -(4-alkoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionic acids were converted into the lactones.

Reduction of β -(4-Alkoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionic Acids.— β -(4-Alkoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionic acid (4 g.) was dissolved in a pressure bottle in 0.1N-KOH (18 c.c.) and diluted to 90 c.c. with distilled water. Raney nickel catalyst (4 g.) was added and after evacuating the bottle, hydrogen was admitted to the mechanically shaken pressure bottle at 20 lbs. pressure. At the end of the reaction (1 hour) the catalyst was filtered, the filtrate acidified with H₂SO₄ (conc., 8 c.c.) and the solution was heated on a water-bath for 1 hour to complete lactonisation of the hydroxy-acid. The product obtained on cooling was kept over saturated solution of sodium bicarbonate to remove acidic impurities. The insoluble lactone was extracted with ether and the ether extract was dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. The lactone obtained on removal of the ether was purified by crystallisation or distilled under reduced pressure (yield 35%).

As a check over the catalytic hydrogenation method, ethyl β -(4-methoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionate was reduced to γ -(4-methoxy-3-xenyl)-butyro lactone by aluminium isopropoxide as follows.

Ethyl β -(4-methoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionate (0.03M) was refluxed with a luminium isopropoxide (0.03 M) in dry isopropyl alcohol (30 c.c.) till the distillate was free from acetone (Adams, "Org. Reactions", Vol. II, p. 196). After removal of isopropyl alcohol HCl (dil.) was added and the organic layer separating was refluxed with alcoholic sodium hydroxide (30 c.c., 20% and alcohol 15 c.c.). After distilling off alcohol, the residue was diluted with water and the neutral impurities were removed with ether. The solution was then acidified with H_2SO_4 (dil., 25%) and more of the acid was added so as to bring the concentration of the acid to about 15%. It was heated on a water-bath for 2 hours and the lactone was isolated as described above. The lactone had m.p. 100° and did not depress the m.p. of the lactone obtained by catalytic reduction. The compounds prepared are shown in the tables.

TABLE I

S.No.	Name of the compound.	Mol. formula.	B.P. or M.P.	Found.	Calc.
1	<i>p</i> -Ethoxydiphenyl	$C_{14}H_{14}O$	Needles from dilute alcohol; 78°	C: 84.7% H: 7.0	84.8% 7.1
2	<i>p</i> - <i>n</i> -Propoxydiphenyl	$C_{15}H_{16}O$	Do; 68°	C: 84.6 H: 7.7	84.9 7.6
3	<i>p</i> - <i>n</i> -Butoxydiphenyl	$C_{16}H_{18}O$	Do; 80°	C: 85.0 H: 8.2	84.9 8.0
4	<i>p</i> - <i>n</i> -Amyloxydiphenyl	$C_{17}H_{20}O$	Do; 58°	C: 85.1 H: 8.6	84.9 8.4

TABLE II

No.	Compounds.	Mol. formula.	B.P. or M.P.	Found.	Calc.
1	Ethyl ester of β -(4-methoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionic acid	$C_{19}H_{20}O_4$	Pale yellow liquid; $207.12^\circ/4$ mm; $n_D^{20} 1.586$	C: 72.8% H: 6.7	73.0% 6.4
2	Semicarbazone of (1) acid	$C_{18}H_{19}O_4N_3$	Needles from dilute alcohol; 186°	Equiv. 343.3	341.0
3	β -(4-Ethoxy-4'-xenoyl)-propionic acid	$C_{18}H_{18}O_4$	Granules from acetic acid; 180°	C: 72.4 H: 6.3 Equiv. 300.5	72.5 6.0 298.0
4	β -(4-Ethoxy-3-xenoyl)-propionic acid	$C_{18}H_{18}O_4$	Granules from dilute alcohol; 165°	C: 72.2 H: 6.2 Equiv. 296.2	72.5 6.0 298.0
5	Ethyl ester of (4)	$C_{20}H_{22}O_4$	Pale yellow liquid; $235.40^\circ/8$ mm; $n_D^{20} 1.598$	C: 73.3 H: 2.8	73.6 3.0
6	Semicarbazone of (4)	$C_{19}H_{21}O_4N_3$	Needles from dilute alcohol; 240°	Equiv. 354.0	355.0
7	β -(4- <i>n</i> -Propoxy-4'-xenoyl)-propionic acid	$C_{19}H_{20}O_4$	Needles from acetic acid; 192°	C: 73.0 H: 6.7 Equiv. 313.	73.1 6.4 312.0

TABLE II (contd.)

S No.	Compounds.	Mol. formula.	B.P. or M.P.	Found.	Calc.
8	β -(4- <i>n</i> -Propoxy-3-xyloyl)-propionic acid	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₄	Small needles from hot water; 154°	C: 72.9% H: 6.6 Equiv. 314.4	73.1% 6.4 312.0
9	Ethyl ester of (8)	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄	Pale yellow liquid; 243-47°/5 mm; n_D^{20} 1.588	C: 74.4 H: 7.3	74.1 7.0
10	Semicarbazone of (8)	C ₂₀ H ₂₃ O ₄ N ₃	Needles from dil. alcohol; 184°	Equiv. 371.4	369.0
11	β -(4- <i>n</i> -Butoxy-4'-xyloyl)-propionic acid	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	Needles from acetic acid; 218°	C: 73.2 H: 6.5 Equiv. 328.0	73.5 6.7 326.0
12	β -(4- <i>n</i> -Butoxy-3-xyloyl)-propionic acid	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₄	Needles from ethyl acetate and petroleum ether; 154°	C: 73.5 H: 6.6 Equiv. 324.2	73.6 6.7 326.0
13	Ethyl ester of (12)	C ₂₂ H ₂₆ O ₄	Pale yellow liquid; 250-55°/10 mm; n_D^{20} 1.588	C: 74.3 H: 7.5	74.6 7.3
14	Semicarbazone of (12)	C ₂₁ H ₂₅ O ₄ N ₃	Needles from dil. alcohol; 214°	Equiv. 386.3	383.0
15	β -(4- <i>n</i> -Amyloxy-4'-xyloyl)-propionic acid	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄	Needles from acetic acid; 197°	C: 74.3 H: 7.3 Equiv. 337.6	74.1 7.3 340.0
16	β -(4- <i>n</i> -Amyloxy-3-xyloyl)-propionic acid	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₄	Needles from dil. alcohol; 185°	C: 74.3 H: 7.3 Equiv. 342.7	74.1 7.0 340.0
17	Ethyl ester of (16)	C ₂₃ H ₂₈ O ₄	Pale yellow liquid; 268-73°/8 mm; n_D^{20} 1.574	C: 76.5 H: 7.8	76.8 7.6
18	Semicarbazone of (16)	C ₂₂ H ₂₇ O ₄ N ₃	Needles from dil. alcohol; 254°	Equiv. 395.3	397.0

TABLE III

S. No.	Compounds.	Mol. formula.	M.P. or B.P.	Found.	Calc.
1	γ -(4-Methoxy-3-xyloyl)-butyro lactone.	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ O ₃	Granules from benzene-petrol; 100°	C: 76.1% H: 6.2 Equiv. 270.1	76.1% 6.0 268.0
2	γ -(4-Ethoxy-3-xyloyl)-butyro lactone.	C ₁₉ H ₁₈ O ₃	Distilled at 125°/2 mm. (ci-bath); 130°	C: 76.5 H: 6.5 Equiv. 280.2	76.6 6.4 282.0
3	γ -(4- <i>n</i> -Propoxy-3-xyloyl)-butyro lactone	C ₁₉ H ₂₀ O ₃	Do; 124°	C: 77.2 H: 6.6 Equiv. 296.5	77.0 6.8 296.0
4	γ -(4- <i>n</i> -Butoxy-3-xyloyl)-butyro lactone.	C ₂₀ H ₂₂ O ₃	Do; 137°	C: 77.6 H: 7.2 Equiv. 307.9	77.4 7.1 310.0
5	γ -(4- <i>n</i> -Amyloxy-3-xyloyl)-butyro lactone.	C ₂₁ H ₂₄ O ₃	Do; 134°	C: 77.5 H: 7.6 Equiv. 322.2	77.8 7.4 324.0.

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